

ISic1434

I.Sicily inscription 1434

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara
Hyblaia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330078

1. Μαρύλο̄ τόδε σᾱμ-
2. α.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644977

EDCS 64800229

PHI 330078

Bibliography

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Manni Piraino, M.T. 1975. Koiné alfabetica fra Siracusa, Megara Iblea e Selinunte?. *Kokalos*. 21: 121-153. At 144 no.8

Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.4

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